

Evaluation of seed vigor of lowland selected rice in Makurdi, Nigeria

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Rice is propagated mainly by using saved seeds in Nigeria. Most farmers save part of their harvest as planting materials for the subsequent season, thus necessitating storage. However, storage sometimes affects seed vigor as shown by the amount and speed of seedling emergence in the field. Thus, it is important to know whether or not differences occur among rice varieties for seed vigor. The existence of such differences among varieties indicates the possibility of improving the longevity of rice in storage.

We studied 50 randomly selected lowland rice genotypes during the 1999 cropping season at the University Experiment Research Station (UERS) to investigate whether or not differences occurred in seed vigor. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications. One hundred seeds of each genotype were planted in 5-m-long single-row plots. Interrow spacing was 0.30 m, with an intrarow spacing of 0.10 m and two seeds hill⁻¹. For each plot, the number of seeds that emerged was counted daily starting from the third day after planting (DAP) until there was no further emergence.

Data obtained were used to compute emergence percentage (E%), emergence index (EI), and emergence rate index (ERI) as follows:

$$E\% = \frac{\text{Total no. of seedlings that emerged}}{\text{Total no. of seeds planted}} \times 100$$

$$EI = \frac{\Sigma (\text{no. of seedlings that emerged in a day}) (\text{DAP})}{\text{Total no. of seedlings that emerged}}$$

$$ERI = \frac{EI}{E\% \text{ (in decimal)}}$$

The data collected underwent analysis of variance (ANOVA) to test for differences among the genotypes.

Seedling emergence started at 3 DAP. The number of seedlings that emerged increased as time progressed, but emergence began to decrease after some time.

Mean squares from ANOVA for the traits studied showed highly significant ($P < 0.01$) genotypic effects for E% and ERI, whereas genotypic effects were not significant ($P > 0.01$) for EI (Table 1).

Table 2 shows the mean E%, EI, and ERI for the various rice genotypes. E% ranged from 43% to 82% with a mean of 60%, EI ranged from 6.6 to 8.2 d with a mean of 7.4 d, whereas ERI ranged from 9.4 to 17.7 d with a mean of 13 d. Generally, therefore, considerable genetic variation occurred among the rice varieties studied in terms of amount and speed of seedling emergence in the field. This indicates the possibility of improving the longevity of rice seed in storage.

Table 1. Mean squares from the analyses of variance for emergence percentage (E%), emergence index (EI), and emergence rate index (ERI) for 50 selected rice varieties.

Source	Mean squares			
	df	E%	EI	ERI
Replication	3	166.2	1.192	13.28
Varieties	49	356.5**	0.487 ns	20.40**
Error	147	180.4	0.507	11.18

ns = nonsignificant. ** = significant at $P = 0.01$.

Table 2. Means of emergence percentage (E%), emergence index (EI), and emergence rate index (ERI) for 50 selected rice varieties.

Variety name	E%	EI (d)	ERI (d)
C1321-9	76.3	7.6	10.0
WITA 4	59.3	7.7	13.6
TOX 3154-136-1-3-2-2	59.3	7.6	12.9
BR1191-10-3-4-2	53.0	7.5	14.6
BR719-26-9-1-1-1	51.8	7.8	15.4
IR65	57.0	7.1	12.8
TOX 3084-136-1-2-2-2	56.8	7.3	13.5
TOX 3440-132-3-3-1	67.8	6.6	10.8
IR51673-50-2-1	53.8	7.3	14.3
BRC16-127-4-1	68.0	7.0	10.7
IR22082-41-2	70.5	7.1	10.9
ITA324	70.8	7.3	10.5
BW311-9	47.3	7.4	16.6
TOX 3880-38-1-1-2	53.5	8.0	15.7
Chanzi (BEIRA)	47.8	8.2	17.3
TOX 3449-84-2-1-3	62.5	7.1	12.0
BR57-282-8-BC83	79.3	7.3	9.4
IR2172-2-3-1	56.8	7.4	14.8
TOX 3052-39-1-2-1	66.0	7.6	12.0
FAROX 319-2-3-1	61.8	7.8	14.1
FOTSIFOT 54 156A	49.5	7.9	17.2
IR43450 5KN-506-2	44.3	7.5	17.2
TOX 3562-61-1-3-2-1-1	46.8	7.0	15.3
Suakoko	52.0	8.0	15.6
De Priuni (Naputo)	81.5	7.0	8.7
FAROX 317-1-1-1	53.3	7.3	15.1
TOX 4008-33-1-2-1	65.8	7.4	11.2
TOX 4004-8-1-2-3	67.3	7.5	12.1
SPT 7108-2-3-3-1	66.0	8.2	13.1
IR54	58.8	6.6	11.6
FARO 44 (S ^s check)	66.8	7.3	11.2
ITA 368 (S check)	72.0	7.5	10.6
IR64	45.3	7.6	17.0
ITA 364	80.3	7.4	9.5
ITA 406	55.3	7.6	13.8
FR-13A	66.0	7.4	11.4
Mahsuri	61.8	7.3	11.8
Petroled Branco (BEIRA)	59.8	7.7	13.5
RPI641-44-4-7	64.0	7.3	12.1
RPI855-402-7-3	53.3	7.1	14.0
RP2071-38-4-1	65.8	7.1	11.6
RP2087-14-7-12-1	70.8	7.4	10.8
Cisadane	60.0	7.4	12.7
TOX 3049-13-1-2-3-1	57.3	7.0	12.6
TOX 3084-136-1-3-1-2	53.0	7.6	14.1
TOX 3098-2-2-1-2-1	58.8	7.1	12.4
TOX 3118-47-1-1	54.5	7.1	13.4
ITA 384	55.5	6.9	12.5
AYT-126 (TRT-26)	68.3	7.1	11.6
Pusa Basmati	42.8	7.5	17.7
LSD (0.05)	18.6	0.99	4.63
Mean	60.3	7.38	13.07
Range	42.75-81.50	6.6-8.2	9.4-17.7

^sS = susceptible.

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Annual General Meeting In Manila

IRRI and Los Baños will host a very important gathering on 28 and 29 October. Five hundred delegates from around the world will visit IRRI and the University of the Philippines Los Baños (UPLB) when they attend the annual general meeting (AGM) of the Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research (CGIAR). The AGM will feature exhibits, a symposium, field tour, and meetings on 30 October-1 November at Shangri-La Hotel in Makati, Metro Manila.

For the first time, the AGM, formerly called International Centers' Week, will be held away from World Bank Headquarters in Washington D.C. Thus, the meeting site will alternate between Washington and the environs of a member center to enhance integration of the CGIAR.

Attended by representatives of the CGIAR centers and donor members, the AGM has traditionally included stakeholders' and business meetings, science awards, and the Crawford lecture on an agricultural topic of global significance, including a number of smaller meetings of the various committees of the consultative group, donors, and international nongovernmental organizations.

The Philippine governments' decision to host the AGM will demonstrate its commitment to the CGIAR and more importantly, attract donor attention to agricultural research in the country. The Philippine Department of Agriculture (DA), specifically the Bureau of Agricultural Research (BAR), has been tasked with organizing the event. As a CGIAR center, IRRI is providing coordination support to the AGM.

The CGIAR, created in 1971, is an association of public and private members supporting a network of 16 Future Harvest centers that work in more than 100 countries to reduce hunger and poverty, improve human nutrition and health, and protect the environment.